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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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TRAINING FUTURE SPEECH THERAPISTS TO ADDRESS SENSORY DISCRIMINATION DISORDERS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: Ushbu maqolada bo'lajak logopedlarni maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kuzatiladigan sensor diskriminatsiya buzilishlarini bartaraf etishga tayyorlashning pedagogik va metodik xususiyatlari yoritilgan. Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida talabalarning kasbiy kompetensiyalarini shakllantirish, ularni muammoni erta aniqlash hamda zamonaviy korreksion metodikalar (xususan, ergoterapiya va sensor integratsiya usullari) bilan ishlashga o'rgatish masalalari ilmiy jihatdan tahlil qilinadi.

Key words: bo'lajak logopedlar, kasbiy tayyorgarlik, kasbiy kompetensiya, sensor diskriminatsiya, maktabgacha yosh, ergoterapiya, maxsus pedagogika.

Annotatsiya: This article highlights the pedagogical and methodological aspects of training future speech therapists to correct sensory discrimination disorders observed in preschool-aged children. It analyzes the formation of professional competencies in higher education students, their training in early problem identification, and their work with modern corrective methods (specifically, occupational therapy and sensory integration techniques). The scientific novelty of the research lies in the integration of neuroplasticity-based sensory integration and occupational therapy methods into traditional speech therapy approaches. This serves to enhance the quality of training for special educators.

Kalit so'zlar: future speech therapists, professional training, professional competence, sensory discrimination, preschool age, occupational therapy, special pedagogy.

Аннотация: В данной статье освещаются педагогические и методические особенности подготовки будущих логопедов к коррекции нарушений сенсорной дискриминации, наблюдаемых у детей дошкольного возраста. Анализируются вопросы формирования профессиональных компетенций у студентов высших учебных заведений, их обучения раннему выявлению проблемы и работе с современными коррекционными методиками (в частности, эрготерапией и методами сенсорной интеграции).

Ключевые слова: будущие логопеды, профессиональная подготовка, профессиональная компетенция, сенсорная дискриминация, дошкольный возраст, эрготерапия, специальная педагогика.

INTRODUCTION

Relevance of the topic: The effectiveness of correctional and pedagogical work with preschool children largely depends on the professional competence of special educators and speech therapists. In childhood, particularly during the preschool years, the brain's process of perceiving and processing information is highly active. However, when children face sensory discrimination disorders, it directly exerts a negative impact on their cognitive, motor, and speech development. Therefore, preparing future speech therapists to identify and address these specific disorders is one of the most urgent tasks in special pedagogy.

Object of the research: The process of professional training of future speech therapists in higher education institutions.

Subject of the research: Developing the methodological and neuropsychological competencies of speech therapists to eliminate sensory discrimination disorders in preschool-aged children.

Aim: To study and implement the pedagogical conditions, methodological approaches, and practical strategies for training future speech therapists to correct sensory discrimination disorders in preschool children.

Tasks: To form neuropsychological knowledge in students; to teach sensory integration and occupational therapy methods; to develop a system of practical exercises.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Issues of sensory integration and discrimination have been widely studied by foreign scholars. In particular, A. J. Ayres ^[1] investigated hidden sensory challenges in children and integration processes in their nervous systems. A. C. Bundy, S. J. Lane, and E. A. Murray ^[2] developed the theoretical and practical foundations of sensory integration. T. A. May-Benson and J. A. Koomar ^[3], as well as B. A. Pfeiffer et al. ^[4], analyzed the effectiveness of sensory integration interventions based on empirical evidence. R. C. Schaaf and Z. Mailloux ^[5] created a clinical guide for applying the Ayres method for children with autism and other developmental disorders. Unlike these studies, our work highlights the issue of adapting and integrating these international experiences into the training process of future speech therapists within the higher education system of Uzbekistan.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

During the research process, methods such as comparative analysis of scientific and educational-methodological literature, pedagogical observation, generalization, and modeling of correctional processes were utilized. To teach students how to diagnose and correct sensory discrimination disorders, theoretical and practical approaches (elements of occupational therapy) were integrated.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Forming neuropsychological competencies in future speech therapists is of paramount importance. To effectively treat sensory discrimination disorders, students must acquire a deep understanding of the central nervous system's ability to differentiate signals. Educational programs should train students to identify when a child perceives stimuli but cannot distinguish their specific details.

Table 1: Types of sensory discrimination disorders and their consequences

Sensory discrimination disorder type	Symptoms students must learn to identify	Consequences for child development
Tactile Discrimination Disorder	Child cannot determine shape, size, or texture of an object without seeing it.	Difficulties with fine motor skills, writing preparation, and self-care.
Visual Discrimination Disorder	Difficulty distinguishing similar shapes or letters. Unable to extract objects from the background.	Severe difficulties in learning to read/write, spatial orientation issues.
Audial Discrimination Disorder	Unable to distinguish between similar phonemes. Cannot isolate educator's voice in noise.	Delay in speech development, phonemic hearing deficits, failure to follow instructions.
Proprioceptive and Vestibular Discrimination	Child does not feel body position well; uses inappropriate force (presses pencil too hard).	Clumsy movements, frequent falls, poor articulation posture.

Within the framework of training students in corrective methodologies and occupational therapy, practical classes are organized. Students practice properly organizing special acoustic and visual environments to develop tactile, auditory, and visual discrimination ^[4].

Table 2: A system of practical exercises learned by future speech therapists

Sensor system	Exercise name	Implementation strategy for the Speech Therapist	Required equipment
Tactile	"Magic Bag"	Guide the child to touch objects with eyes closed and verbalize their tactile properties to build sensory-speech connections.	Small bag, ball, cube, cotton, coin.
Visual	"Shadow Game"	Instruct the child to align real figures with their shadows, prompting them to name the objects to enhance visual-verbal integration.	Paper scraps, toy figures.
Audial	"Noisy Boxes"	Teach the child to shake boxes and distinguish sounds, crucial for developing phonemic awareness for future speech correction.	4-5 small containers (kinder-surprise containers), cereals.
Proprioceptive	"Heavy-Light"	Task the child with carrying varying weights to help them regulate muscle tone, which indirectly supports oral-motor control.	Books, pillows, water bottles.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, preparing future speech therapists to address sensory discrimination disorders in preschool children is a complex but essential pedagogical task. The inclusion of neuropsychological theory, sensory integration techniques, and occupational therapy into the university curriculum ensures that graduates possess the comprehensive competencies required to meet the demands of modern special education.

Recommendations:

1. Include the subject "Fundamentals of Sensory Integration and Occupational Therapy" in the curricula of the "Special Pedagogy" and "Speech Therapy" fields in higher education institutions.
2. Increase practical laboratory classes based on neuroplasticity for students.
3. Develop special methodological manuals for working with parents and actively involve students in this process.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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